

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHYTOCHEMICALS IN *ERANTHEMUM CAPENSE* L. AND *ERANTHEMUM ROSEUM* (VAHL)

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Abstract:

Qualitative phytochemical analysis is crucial for the identification of phytochemical constituents in medicinal plants, as their medicinal value is primarily attributed to the presence of specific bioactive compounds. The objective of the present study was to investigate the presence of phytochemical constituents in aqueous, methanolic, acetone and petroleum ether extracts of the roots, stems and leaves of two *Eranthemum* species, namely *E. capense* and *E. roseum*. In this analysis, the presence of alkaloids, anthocyanins, betacyanins, cardiac glycosides, coumarins, flavonoids, glycosides, phenols, quinones, saponins, steroids, tannins and terpenoids was screened. Among the extracts tested, the methanolic extract showed the highest number of phytochemicals, followed by acetone, petroleum ether, and aqueous extracts. The positive results obtained in various phytochemical tests indicate that *Eranthemum* species are important due to the presence of diverse bioactive constituents.

Keywords: *Acanthaceae*, *Eranthemum*, Phytochemical, Qualitative Screening.

1. Introduction

The *Acanthaceae* is a large family of dicotyledonous flowering plants comprising 346 genera and over 4,300 species distributed worldwide. There is increasing interest in indigenous medicinal plants for their accurate identification, classification, and therapeutic applications. Important secondary metabolites such as glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids, triterpenoids, fatty acid methyl esters and fatty acids are present in this family (1). Plants of the *Acanthaceae* family are widely utilized as commercial crops, ornamentals, medicinal plants, food sources and natural colorants. Numerous species exhibit medicinal properties and are used in the treatment of ailments such as beriberi, paralysis, pain, toothache, asthma and cough (2). The Western Ghats are a major biodiversity hotspot with a rich diversity of plant species. Commonly known as the Sahyadri Mountains, they extend for about 1,600

kilometers along the western coast of India. This region is well known for its extensive range of medicinal plants and is estimated to harbour over 7,500 species of flowering plants. Since the dawn of human civilization, medicinal plants have been used for a variety of therapeutic purposes (3).

Eranthemum L. belongs to the family *Acanthaceae*. Approximately 23 species are distributed worldwide, of which about 15 species are found in India. In the Western Ghats, around five species are reported. *E. capense* is distributed across India, Myanmar and Sri Lanka (4, 5, 6). It is a subshrub endemic to Peninsular India with a wide distribution in regions such as Goa, Chikmagalur, Tamil Nadu, Mangalore, Mysore and Udupi. Ethnobotanically, *E. capense* is used in various regions of India for its medicinal properties. In Kerala, the leaves are used for their anti-inflammatory activity and in the treatment of dysentery and diabetes (7, 8). In the Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh, plant latex is used to treat blisters and boils (9). In South India, the plant is also used in traditional medicine for managing typhoid (10). Qualitative phytochemical screening of the methanolic extract of *E. capense* has revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids and terpenoids (11).

E. roseum is native to Bangladesh and India (4). Its habitat includes moist deciduous forests and open areas (12, 13). In India, particularly in the South-Western Satpuda Hills, Leghapani, a decoction of the whole *E. roseum* plant is traditionally used for treatment of leg pain and swellings (14). In South India, the roots and leaves of *E. roseum* are traditionally used to treat skin diseases (15, 16). In Maharashtra, vertigo is treated using the root, either in paste form or by inhaling its odor (17). In the same region, *E. roseum* paste is used to treat leucoderma; it is also applied to heal foot cracks, reduce pain and promote wound healing (18, 19). The juice of *E. roseum* has long been used in Maharashtra to treat stomach aches and diabetes (20–23). In several regions of India, *E. roseum* has been widely utilized to manage various conditions, including fever, acidity, typhoid, leucorrhea, inflammation, jaundice, body heat, ulcers and snake bites (24–33). A decoction of the flowers is traditionally used in Maharashtra to treat irregular menstruation (34). Phytochemical studies indicate that the leaves of *E. roseum* contain flavonoids such as 7-OMe apigenin, 7,4'-diOMe luteolin and 7,3',4'-triOMe luteolin. The roots contain saponin glycosides, carbohydrates, proteins, steroidal saponins and terpenoids, while the flowers are rich in flavonoids and anthocyanins (13). Further phytochemical investigations have confirmed the presence of steroidal saponin glycosides in the roots (35). Aqueous and methanolic extracts of the roots have been reported to contain saponins, glycosides, polysaccharides and proteins, whereas petroleum ether and chloroform extracts contain steroidal saponins (12, 13). Phytochemicals constitute a large group of compounds found in plants, including primary and secondary metabolites that support various biological processes such as plant growth, defense mechanisms and protection (36, 37). Qualitative phytochemical analysis is used to detect the presence of various bioactive compounds in plant extracts, including alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, glycosides, volatile oils and phenolic compounds.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Collection of plant materials

Eranthemum species were collected from different localities. The plant materials were taxonomically identified and authenticated by the Department of Botany, The New College, Kolhapur. The roots, stems and leaves were cleaned with tap water. To prevent the degradation of heat-sensitive phytoconstituents, the collected plant materials were shade-dried at room temperature. After drying, the plant parts were finely powdered using an electric mixer. The dried material was then sieved to obtain a uniform fine powder for extraction. The powder was stored in a plastic jar with an airtight lid until further use.

2.2 Preparation of sample

For qualitative phytochemical analysis, samples were prepared by dissolving 5 g of plant material powder in 50 ml of solvent. The mixture was kept on an electric shaker (Thenmotek OS-8101) at a rotating speed of 150 rpm for 24 hours (overnight). It was then first filtered through a double layer of muslin cloth, followed by filtration using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. Different solvents were used for qualitative phytochemical analysis. Polar solvents dissolve polar compounds, whereas non-polar solvents dissolve non-polar compounds. Thus, different phytochemicals are extracted using different solvents based on their polarity. In this study, four solvents water, methanol, acetone and petroleum ether were used. Plant material can be extracted using various methods to isolate phytochemicals. The shaker extraction method was chosen due to its simplicity and efficiency, as it enhances the interaction between the plant material and the solvent, thereby increasing the extraction yield. All procedures were carried out under laboratory conditions.

2.3 Phytochemical test

Qualitative phytochemical tests used in this study were compiled from various published sources. Table 1 presents the preliminary tests conducted for the identification of different phytochemicals.

Table 1: Qualitative Tests for Phytochemical Screening

Phytochemical Class	Test	Reference
Carbohydrates	Barfoed's Test	38, 39
	Seliwanoff's Test	39, 40
	Resorcinol Test	41, 42
Alkaloids	Hager's Test	38, 39, 43
	Mayer's Test	38, 42, 44, 45
	Wagener's Test	42, 46
Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent Test	46-49
	Lead acetate Test	44, 46, 47, 50, 51
	Ferric chloride Test	47
Phenolic Compound	Ferric chloride Test	38, 44
	Lead acetate Test	38
	Ellagic Acid Test	52, 53
Tannins	Braymer's Test	54, 55
	10% NaOH Test	54
Reducing Sugar	Benedict's Test	38, 46, 54
	Fehling's Test	38, 54
Cardiac glycosides	Keller - Killani Test	54, 56
	Baljet's Test	57, 58
Saponins	Foam Test	44
Phytosterols	Salkowski's Test	44, 54
Phlobatannins	HCL Test	42, 59
Anthraquinones	Borntrager's Test	49, 55, 59
Glycosides	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ Test	52, 53
Volatile Oil		60

3. Result and Discussion

Alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, cardiac glycosides, tannins, glycosides, saponins, anthraquinones, phytosterols, volatile oils, carbohydrates and proteins were identified among the phytochemicals present in various extracts of *E. capense* and *E. roseum*, as summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Qualitative Phytochemical analysis of *Eranthemum capense*

<i>E. capense</i> Leaves					<i>E. capense</i> Stem					<i>E. capense</i> Root			
Test	Methanol	Aqueous	Petroleum Ether	Acetone	Methanol	Aqueous	Petroleum Ether	Acetone	Methanol	Aqueous	Petroleum Ether	Acetone	
Carbohydrates													
Barfoed's Test	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Seliwanoff's Test	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Resorcinol Test	+++	+	-	+	++	+	-	-	+	++	-	-	
Alkaloids													
Hager's Test	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Mayer's Test	-	-	-	+	++	-	+++	+	++	-	++	+	
Wagener's Test	-	+	+	++	+	+	+	+	++	+	++	+	
Flavonoids													
Alkaline reagent Test	+	+	+	++	-	+	+	++	+	+	+	+++	
Lead acetate Test	-	-	+	-	+++	-	-	+++	+++	-	-	+++	
Ferric chloride Test	+++	+	-	++	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Phenolic Compound													
Ferric chloride Test	+++	-	-	+++	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	
Lead acetate Test	-	+	+	-	+++	-	++	-	+	+	+	+++	
Ellagic Acid Test	-	+	-	+++	-	+	-	+++	-	-	-	-	

Tannins														
Braymer's Test	+++	-	-	+		+	++	-	-		-	-	-	-
10% NaOH Test	+	+	+	++		+++	-	+	+		+++	-	+	+
Reducing Sugar														
Benedict's Test	++	++	-	-		+	-	-	-		++	-	-	-
Fehling's Test	-	+	-	-		-	++	-	+		+	-	+	-
Cardiac glycosides														
Keller – Killani Test	-	-	-	-		++	-	+	-		-	-	-	-
Baljet's Test	+++	+	-			-	++	-	+		+++	++	-	-
Saponins														
Foam Test	++	+	-	+		+	++	-	-		+	++	-	-
Phytosterols														
Salkowski's Test	++	-	-	-		+++	-	+++			++	-	-	-
Phlobatannins														
HCL Test	-	+	-	-		-	+	-	-		-	+	-	-
Anthraquinones														
Borntrager's Test	-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-
Glycosides														
Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ Test	++	-	-	-		-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-
Volatile Oil														
	-	-	++	-		+	-	++	-		+	-	++	+

+++ = High, ++ = Moderate, + = Slight, - = Negative

Qualitative phytochemical screening of *Eranthemum capense* revealed a varied distribution of bioactive constituents in the leaves, stems and roots, depending on the solvent used. In the leaves, the methanolic extract contained carbohydrates, flavonoids, tannins, reducing sugars, saponins, phytosterols and phenolic compounds, while the aqueous extract showed a moderate presence of reducing sugars, carbohydrates and phenolic compounds. The

petroleum ether extract showed the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds and volatile oils, whereas the acetone extract contained alkaloids along with flavonoids, phenolic compounds and tannins. The methanolic extract of the stem exhibited flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins and phytosterols. The aqueous extract contained reducing sugars, tannins and cardiac glycosides, while the petroleum ether extract revealed the presence of flavonoids and alkaloids. The acetone extract showed flavonoids and phenolic compounds. In the roots, the methanolic extract was rich in alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, reducing sugars, phytosterols and cardiac glycosides. The aqueous extract contained carbohydrates, saponins and cardiac glycosides, whereas the petroleum ether extract showed alkaloids and volatile oils. The acetone extract contained flavonoids and phenolic compounds.

Table 3: Qualitative Phytochemical analysis of *Eranthemum roseum*

<i>E. roseum</i> Leaves					<i>E. roseum</i> Stem					<i>E. roseum</i> Root				
Test	Methanol	Aqueous	Petroleum Ether	Acetone	Methanol	Aqueous	Petroleum Ether	Acetone	Methanol	Aqueous	Petroleum Ether	Acetone		
Carbohydrates														
Barfoed's Test	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Seliwanoff's Test	-	++	-	-	-	++	-	-	-	++	-	-		
Resorcinol Test	+	+++	-	-	-	++	-	-	-	++	-	-		
Alkaloids														
Hager's Test	+++	-	+	-	++	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Mayer's Test	+++	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-	++	-	+	+		
Wagner's Test	+++	-	++	-	++	-	+	-	+++	-	++	+		
Flavonoids														
Alkaline reagent Test	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+++		
Lead acetate Test	+++	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-		
Ferric chloride Test	+++	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-		

Phenolic Compound														
Ferric chloride Test	+++	-	-	+++		-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-
Lead acetate Test	+	-	-	-		+	-	-	+++		+++	-	-	+
Ellagic Acid Test	-	-	-	+++		-	-	-	-		+++	-	-	-
Tannins														
Braymer's Test	+	-	-	++		-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-
10% NaOH Test	+	-	-	+++		-	-	+	+++		-	-	-	+++
Reducing Sugar														
Benedict's Test	+++	++	-	+		+++	++	-	+		-	-	-	-
Fehling's Test	++	-	-	-		-	+	-	-		-	+	-	-
Cardiac glycosides														
Keller – Killani Test	+++	-	-	+++		-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-
Baljet's Test	-	-	-	-		+++	-	-	++		+++	-	-	+++
Saponins														
Foam Test	-	++	-	-		-	+	-	-		+	++	-	-
Phytosterols														
Salkowski's Test	-	-	-	-		-	-	+++	-		-	-	-	-
Phlobatannins														
HCL Test	-	+	-	-		-	+	-	-		-	+	-	-
Anthraquinones														
Borntrager's Test	-	+	-	-		-	+	-	-		-	-	-	-
Glycosides														
Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ Test	-	+++	+++	-		++	++	-	-		-	-	+++	++
Volatile Oil														
	-	-	+++	-		+++	-	-	-		+++	-	-	-

+++ = High, ++ = Moderate, + = Slight, - = Negative

The distribution of phytochemical compounds varied across different plant parts and solvent extracts. In the leaves, the methanolic extract contained flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, reducing sugars and cardiac glycosides, while the aqueous extract showed the presence of carbohydrates, reducing sugars, saponins and glycosides. The petroleum ether extract contained alkaloids, glycosides and volatile oils, whereas the acetone extract was characterized by tannins, phenolic compounds and cardiac glycosides. In the stem, the methanolic extract exhibited alkaloids, flavonoids, reducing sugars, phytosterols, glycosides, cardiac glycosides and volatile oils. The aqueous extract contained carbohydrates, reducing sugars and glycosides, while the petroleum ether extract showed alkaloids and glycosides. The acetone extract contained tannins, phenolic compounds and cardiac glycosides. In the roots, the methanolic extract was rich in alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, volatile oils and cardiac glycosides. The aqueous extract contained carbohydrates and saponins, whereas the petroleum ether extract showed flavonoids, glycosides and cardiac glycosides. The acetone extract contained flavonoids, tannins, glycosides and cardiac glycosides. Both *E. capense* and *E. roseum* are rich in diverse bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, phenolic compounds, alkaloids, tannins, reducing sugars, phytosterols, cardiac glycosides, glycosides and volatile oils, indicating their potential pharmacological significance.

Conclusion

The qualitative phytochemical screening of *E. roseum* and *E. capense* revealed a broad spectrum of bioactive constituents distributed in the leaves, stems and roots across different solvent extracts. In both species, methanolic extracts exhibited the highest phytochemical diversity, indicating their superior efficiency in extracting secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, cardiac glycosides, reducing sugars, phytosterols and volatile oils. Aqueous extracts were mainly characterized by the presence of carbohydrates, reducing sugars, saponins and glycosides, whereas petroleum ether extracts predominantly contained non-polar compounds such as volatile oils, along with certain alkaloids and flavonoids. Acetone extracts showed moderate phytochemical diversity, including tannins, phenolic compounds, glycosides and cardiac glycosides. The consistent occurrence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds across most extracts of both species suggests their abundance and possible contribution to biological activity. Overall, the results indicate the phytochemical richness of *E. roseum* and *E. capense*, thereby providing a scientific basis for further studies on the isolation, characterization and biological evaluation of their active constituents. Further research may lead to the isolation of additional bioactive compounds from selected *Eranthemum* species, which could be utilized for medicinal purposes in the future.

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Author contributions

PVP was responsible for data collection, experimentation, writing and compilation and also critically reviewed and revised the manuscript as required. SPD reviewed the manuscript. SAD provided supervision, technical guidance and final editing. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors.

Conflict of interest

All authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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